

1 **Polygyny can increase rather than decrease genetic diversity**
2 **contributed by males relative to females: evidence from red**
3 **deer**

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18 POLYGYNY MAINTAINS GENETIC DIVERSITY

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24 **Abstract**

25 Polygyny is expected to erode genetic variability by reducing the diversity of genetic contribution
26 of males to the next generation, although empirical evidence shows that genetic variability in
27 polygynous populations is not lost as rapidly as expected. We used microsatellite markers to study
28 the genetic variability transmitted by mothers and fathers to offspring during a reproductive season
29 in wild populations of a polygynous mammal, the red deer. Contrary to expectations, we found that
30 males contributed more genetic diversity than females. Also, we compared study populations with
31 different degrees of polygyny to find that polygyny was not related to a decrease in genetic diversity
32 contributed by males. On the contrary, when population genetic diversity was relatively low,
33 polygyny associated with higher genetic diversity of paternal lineage. Our results show that sexual
34 selection, by favouring heterozygote individuals, may compensate the potential reduction of
35 effective population size caused by polygyny, thus contributing to explain why genetic diversity is
36 not depleted in polygynous systems.

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47 **Introduction**

48 Theory predicts that the lower the number of males that take part in reproduction with respect to
49 females, the smaller the effective population size with respect to census size (Wright 1938; Chesser
50 1991; Nunney 1991, 1993). Populations with small effective size tend to experience reductions of
51 their genetic diversity through generations (Wright 1931, 1938; Nei et al. 1975; Young et al. 1996).
52 Therefore, polygyny is expected to reduce genetic diversity due to its negative effects on effective
53 population size (Briton et al. 1994). In agreement with this assumption, broadly used estimations of
54 effective population size to predict genetic diversity loss are based on the variance in reproductive
55 success among individuals in the population (Nunney 1991, 1993; Nunney & Elam 1994). However,
56 these estimations assume that breeding individuals represent a random sample of the genetic
57 diversity present in the adult population, an assumption that is likely violated if selection favours
58 the reproduction of the most genetically diverse individuals.

59 Empirical evidence shows that genetic variability in natural populations is not lost as rapidly
60 as expected (see, e.g. Wenink et al. 1998; Hmwe et al. 2006; Keaeuffer et al. 2007). Selective
61 processes such as the interaction with predators and parasites may confer disadvantages to
62 homozygous individuals (Keller & Waller 2002) and contribute to the maintenance of genetic
63 diversity (Lewontin et al. 1978). In polygynous species, selection may be much more intense in
64 males than in females and there is evidence that sexual selection may favour heterozygous males
65 (Anderson 1994; Rose et al. 1998; Slate et al. 2000). Also, male–male competition has been shown
66 to enhance selection against inbred individuals (Meagher et al. 2000). If sexual selection favours
67 genetically diverse males, then the potential loss of genetic variability when only few males take
68 part in reproduction might be compensated by the elevated genetic variability of the breeding males.

69 Surprisingly, and despite the largely accepted assumption that polygyny should reduce
70 genetic diversity transmitted by males (Wright 1938; Chesser 1991; Briton et al. 1994), we are
71 unaware of any study that has investigated the relative roles of males and females in the genetic
72 variability transmitted to the next generation under a polygynous breeding system in natural
73 conditions. The objective of this work was to analyse genetic diversity contributed by males and
74 females within a breeding season in a polygynous species, the Iberian red deer (*Cervus elaphus*
75 *hispanicus*), for which we can also compare study areas with different levels of polygyny to study
76 the effect of polygyny over genetic diversity contributed by males.

77

78 **Methods**

79 *Study area and data collection*

80 The study was conducted between 2004 and 2006 in 20 areas located in Mediterranean ecosystems
81 in Southwestern Spain (throughout Extremadura and Andalucía regions). Each area was studied
82 only in one of the study years. Study areas averaged c. 500 ha in size and were located within
83 private hunting estates. Every area typically included a part of a mountain range covered by
84 Mediterranean scrub (*Cistus* spp., *Erica* spp., *Genista hirsuta*, *Lavandula* spp.) and forest (*Quercus*
85 spp., *Arbutus unedo*, *Olea europaea*, *Phyllirea* spp.) and a lower and flatter land, covered by open
86 oak woodland or *dehesa* (*Quercus* spp.). Areas covered by Mediterranean scrub and forest
87 constitute feeding and refuge areas. *Dehesas* constitute feeding areas and rutting arenas.

88 During the rutting period, we carried out car journeys along rut arenas and counted
89 individuals to determine the sex ratio in every estate. All counts were performed by the same
90 observer at the peak of the rut. We have already shown that most red deer clump at this time in
91 mating areas (Carranza & Valencia 1999), so we considered that our counts were useful to estimate
92 the relative numbers of males and females interacting during the rut. We obtained tissue samples

93 from specimens legally culled by hunters in these areas the next hunting period. Sampled
94 individuals in each area belonged to a Mediterranean forest zone associated with a particular rutting
95 arena that we previously characterized on the basis of observations during the rutting season.
96 Therefore, our data were collected from groups of animals that could interact during the previous
97 rutting period within a mating behavioural unit. The hunting procedure was in all cases the Spanish
98 ‘montería’ or a similar type of hunt. In this type of hunt, packs of dogs are released within a shrub
99 area to move the deer outwards to the sites where hunters are placed. Normally, every male deer of
100 2 years or more, or every female of any age, can be shot in commercial hunting focused on stags or
101 in management hunt aimed at reducing density of hinds, respectively. Under these conditions, there
102 is little opportunity for hunting bias to particular individuals, and montería has been shown to be the
103 less-biased procedure to obtain data from hunted red deer (Martínez et al. 2005). This study never
104 provoked hunters to shoot additional deer (see also Carranza et al. 2004).

105 From the 20 study areas, we obtained samples of 292 stags, 309 pregnant hinds and their
106 309 foetuses. We determined the proportion of pregnant females by inspection of the reproductive
107 tracts. In our populations, overall proportion of pregnant females was 0.78 (338 pregnant out of 433
108 inspected females). We used in the analyses only those pregnant females whose foetuses were
109 sufficiently developed to obtain tissue samples. Samples of individuals consisted of pieces of
110 muscle that were preserved frozen at -20°C . Genomic DNA was purified by proteinase K digestion
111 and salting out procedure (Millar et al. 1988).

112

113 *Microsatellite genotyping*

114 We typed individuals at 12 microsatellite loci: OarFCB193, OarCP26, OarFCB304, CelJP38,
115 CelJP15, TGLA94, TGLA53, BM1818, CSSM22, CSSM16, ILSTS06, CSPS115 (Coulson et al.
116 1998; Marshall et al. 1998; Bonnet et al. 2002; Martínez et al. 2002; Kuehn et al. 2003). After

117 polymerase chain reaction (PCR), we used ABI 3130 DNA sequencer and GeneMapper software
118 (Applied Biosystems) to determine allele sizes. We combined the markers in five multiplex or
119 simplex PCRs: 1×6 , 1×3 and 3×1 (number of PCRs \times number of markers). For each of five
120 PCRs we created a microsatellite panel within GeneMapper software. For each panel we included
121 all our typed samples as reference samples. We used Auto Bin function of GeneMapper to convert
122 allele sizes into allele classes. To assess the accuracy of genotyping, 60 individuals were retyped
123 returning identical genotypes. These retyped individuals included males, females and foetuses, and
124 belonged to our sample stock (most of them included in this work). Retyped individuals were
125 selected from those individuals without missing genotypes. For the samples used in this study,
126 coincidence of at least one allele between a mother and her foetus was 99.6%. This percentage
127 could be due to manual errors, mutations or some null alleles. Overall, our rate of missing data was
128 7.2%.

129 *Estimating genetic diversity*

130 We constructed paternal and maternal half genotypes of foetuses by comparing each foetus'
131 genotype with its mother's genotype (Jones et al. 2001). There were 13% cases of ambiguity (i.e.
132 foetus and mother shared the same heterozygous genotype) (Fuimera & Asmussen 2001). In these
133 cases, we assigned the alleles to paternal lineage at random but with a probability proportional to
134 the relative frequency of the ambiguous alleles in the males of the population which the foetus
135 belongs to. Two ploidy levels were created: diploid individuals (stags and hinds) and haploid
136 lineages (paternally inherited genetic component in foetuses or paternal lineage, and maternally
137 inherited genetic component in foetuses or maternal lineage). Thus, we obtained four genotype sets
138 (two diploids and two haploids). To calculate genetic diversity of different genotype sets with both
139 ploidy levels, we used three different indices. One of them, the effective allele number computed as
140 the sum of the squared frequencies of alleles (Kimura & Crow 1964), yielded almost identical

141 results than Shannon's diversity index, so we finally omitted it. Thus, we present the results for the
 142 two following indices:

143 1 Shannon's diversity index (Lewontin 1972; see also Lowe et al. 2004) as:

$$144 \quad H = - \sum p_i \ln(p_i)$$

145 where p_i is the proportion of the i allele in the genotype set. This index takes into account the
 146 number of different alleles and the frequency of each allele.

147 2 Simpson's diversity index (Simpson 1949; see also Lowe et al. 2004) as:

$$148 \quad Dg = 1 - \{ \sum [n_i (n_i - 1)] / N(N-1) \}$$

149 where n_i is the absolute frequency (count) of allele i within a sample of N genotypes (diploid
 150 genomes contribute with two genotypes per locus). This index varies from 0 to 1 and mainly
 151 captures for a given locus how evenly frequencies distribute throughout different alleles. This index
 152 includes some correction by the maximum number of genotypes (N) and hence, it is little sensitive
 153 to sample size or ploidy (Lowe et al. 2004).

154 Both indices provide complementary information. Shannon index is a classical measurement
 155 of diversity in many fields, it being in the present use highly sensitive to the number of genotypes
 156 (hence to sample size and ploidy), whereas Simpson index is less sensitive to sample size or ploidy
 157 and mostly captures the evenness of the distribution of allele frequencies (Lowe et al. 2004).

158 Simpson index is very similar to gene diversity or expected heterozygosity (Nei 1973), although the
 159 term heterozygosity may not be appropriate when applying it to haploid genotypes. Here we use the
 160 specific names of each index (Shannon and Simpson) and the more general term genetic diversity
 161 when referring to the results in general from either index. We computed both indices for the four
 162 sets of genotypes (adult stags, adult hinds, paternal lineage and maternal lineage of foetuses).

163 Indices were calculated individually for samples of each study area (20) and each microsatellite
 164 marker (12), hence resulting in 20×12 data points for each of the four sets of genotypes. We

165 included in calculations a set of genotypes for a microsatellite locus only if this set contained at
166 least five genotypes, to avoid computing diversity indices with very low sample size, so the figure
167 of 20×12 was slightly lower in some cases.

168

169 *Genetically connected areas*

170 To establish genetically connected areas in our data set, we used Structure 2.0 (Pritchard et al.
171 2000). This program uses Bayesian methodology to determine the level of genetic substructure in
172 the data set independently of sampling areas (see Supporting information for detailed methods and
173 results on genetically connected areas).

174

175 *Polygyny degree*

176 To estimate the polygyny degree in our study populations, we first obtained the observed number of
177 fathers in each sample of fetuses from each population by using the Parentage software (Emery et
178 al. 2001). This program uses a combination of Markov chain Monte Carlo techniques to select the
179 most probable set of fathers from the distribution of parents and sibling relationships that could
180 have produced the observed sample. Second, we used computer simulations to obtain the expected
181 number of fathers for the same sample of fetuses according to the structure of the population (adult
182 sex ratio), assuming random mating and equiprobability of paternity for all adult males. Then we
183 computed the polygyny level index for each population by dividing the expected number of fathers
184 by the genetically observed one. This index increases as the number of sires decreases with respect
185 to the number of expected fathers under no competitive conditions, and hence it captures the level
186 of competition among males in the population (detailed method and results of parentage analysis
187 and polygyny degree in Supporting information).

188

189 *Statistical analyses*

190 To investigate whether paternally and maternally inherited genetic diversity of foetuses differed, we
191 used repeated measures linear mixed models fitted by restricted maximum likelihood (REML: spss
192 software version 13, SPSS Inc.). The dependent variables were the foetuses' diversity indices (both
193 Shannon and Simpson indices) calculated individually for loci within parental lineage within estates
194 ($2 \times 12 \times 20$ data points in total). Microsatellite genetic markers and estates were used to define the
195 independent subjects ($N = 12 \times 20$) for the repeated measures effect (maternal and paternal lineage
196 for each marker and estate), since the two lineage diversity indices for the same locus within estate
197 may be correlated. Male or female adult genetic diversity was included as covariate for each
198 respective lineage and microsatellite genetic markers and estates were also introduced in the models
199 as random factors. We chose the sum of squares type III and the 'unstructured' covariance structure
200 for repeated effects. These models showed the best-fitting values of the information criteria [-2
201 restricted log likelihood and AIC (Akaike's information criterion)]. The final models included the
202 fixed factor (parental lineage), the covariate and the interaction between them. Similar repeated
203 measures mixed models were used to compare adults' genetic diversity and that of the parental
204 lineage of foetuses (males vs. paternal lineage and females vs. maternal lineage).

205 To investigate the effect of polygyny on offspring genetic diversity, we conducted other
206 mixed models by using only the paternal lineage's genetic diversity as dependent variable and
207 males' genetic diversity as covariate. The predicted variable (polygyny values calculated for each
208 estate) was categorized into two levels: low polygyny (values ranging from 0.97 to 1.20) and high
209 polygyny (values ranging from 1.30 to 1.82) and added to the model as a fixed effect. Microsatellite
210 genetic markers and estates were introduced in the models as random factors.

211

212 *Simulations*

213 We made computer simulations to see whether homozygous disadvantage could increase genetic
214 diversity under a polygynous mating system. We used our samples of N_i adult males from the 20
215 populations and computed genetic diversity (both indices). From these initial populations, we took a
216 sample of males $m_i = \text{number of fetuses}/2$ in order to generate a number of genotypes similar to that
217 in the sample of paternal lineages for each population. Sampling of m_i males was performed with
218 replacement, so any individual male could be represented more than once in the sample, as in a
219 polygynous system. We performed three simulations with the following criteria: (i) polygyny
220 without selection (random choice of m_i males to breed); (ii) polygyny with low homozygous
221 disadvantage (random choice of m_i males after removing the $(N_i - m_i)/2$ more homozygous
222 individuals in each population); and (iii) polygyny with strong homozygous disadvantage (random
223 choice of m_i males after removing the $N_i - m_i$ more homozygous individuals in each population).
224 Each simulation type was repeated 10 times.

225

226 **Results**

227 *Genetic diversity transmitted by males and females within populations*

228 For both indices, genetic diversity did not differ between adult males and females within
229 populations (Fig. 1a, b). When comparing adults and parental lineage of foetuses by using the
230 Shannon index, the results showed that the genetic diversity of adults was higher than that obtained
231 for parental lineage of foetuses (mean \pm SE: adult males = 1.386 ± 0.028 , paternal lineage of
232 foetuses = 1.309 ± 0.027 ; adult females = 1.394 ± 0.026 , maternal lineage of foetuses = $1.220 \pm$
233 0.027 ; Table 1a, Fig. 1a). However, for Simpson index, paternally inherited genetic diversity was
234 not lower but even significantly higher than the diversity of adult males (mean \pm SE: adult males =
235 0.710 ± 0.010 , paternal lineage = 0.732 ± 0.010 ; adult females = 0.710 ± 0.010 , maternal lineage =
236 0.695 ± 0.011 ; Table 1b, Fig. 1b). When comparing both parental lineages of foetuses, our results

237 showed that, contrary to expectations for a polygynous species, fetuses' genetic diversity inherited
238 from paternal lineage was notably higher than genetic diversity inherited from maternal lineage,
239 regardless the index of genetic diversity that we used (Table 2a and b, Fig. 1a and b). Furthermore,
240 genetic diversity contributed by males with respect to females' contribution was higher in situations
241 of low genetic diversity (see estimates for slope differences in Table 2a and b).

242 Our analyses assumed that sampled adult males for each study area represent the genetic
243 composition of males interacting in the arena during the previous rutting period. We know that stags
244 move during the rut to mating arenas that may be apart from the ranges that they use during the rest
245 of the year (Clutton-Brock et al. 1982). If some of the males who mated in a particular area
246 belonged to adjacent areas, genetic diversity of sampled males in a particular area may not include
247 such wandering males and hence it may underestimate the genetic diversity of males actually
248 interacting during the rut (Wahlund effect: Wahlund 1928). To avoid this problem, we repeated the
249 analyses at a higher spatial scale, grouping areas at the level for which we could safely assume no
250 movement of individuals between them, either because the areas were fenced estates that prevent
251 deer movement between them or because there were geographical distances or discontinuities that
252 produce fragmentation of populations which was assessed on the basis of gene flow (see Supporting
253 Information). For this new grouping of areas ($N = 12$ instead of 20), the results were almost
254 identical: all mean diversity values were higher as a consequence of the larger size of the areas
255 (Shannon index: males mean \pm SE = 1.481 ± 0.035 , females mean \pm SE = 1.491 ± 0.033 , paternal
256 lineage of fetuses mean \pm SE = 1.402 ± 0.033 , maternal lineage of fetuses mean \pm SE = $1.337 \pm$
257 0.032 ; Simpson index: males mean \pm SE = 0.732 ± 0.012 , females mean \pm SE = 0.734 ± 0.011 ,
258 paternal lineage of fetuses mean \pm SE = 0.749 ± 0.013 , maternal lineage of fetuses mean \pm SE =
259 0.718 ± 0.013), but the relationship between them maintained largely unaffected (Table3).

260

261 *Simulation results*

262 To see whether our previous results could be achieved by a mechanism of selective disadvantage of
263 homozygous males in a polygynous system, we performed computer simulations. Simulation results
264 show that polygyny without selection decreases genetic diversity due to a reduction of genotype
265 sample size. However, this decrease compensated as polygyny included a stronger selective
266 disadvantage for homozygotes (Fig.2a, b). For Simpson index, selection against homozygotes
267 increased genetic diversity even above that of all males in the population due to the increase of the
268 relative frequency of rare alleles compared to most common alleles (Fig. 2b).

269

270 *Effects of polygyny*

271 Polygyny level was not related to a decrease in genetic diversity transmitted by males, as it might be
272 expected. For Shannon's index, in situations of low genetic diversity, males transmitted more
273 genetic diversity under high polygyny conditions than under low polygyny conditions (Fig. 3, Table
274 4a). Conversely, in situations of high genetic diversity this result reverted (Fig. 3, Table 4a). For
275 Simpson's index, the pattern was the same although the effect was not significant (Table 4b).

276

277 **Discussion**

278 We have shown for the first time that males in a polygynous species transmit more genetic diversity
279 than females, especially in situations of low population genetic diversity. This result maintained
280 when our study populations were grouped in larger, genetically connected areas, indicating that the
281 higher genetic diversity in paternal lineage compared with maternal lineage was not caused by
282 rutting males immigrating from other areas. Also, paternally transmitted genetic diversity was not
283 only higher than maternally transmitted one, but it was also higher than the genetic diversity in the
284 population of adults when we used Simpson index to estimate genetic diversity, indicating that

285 allele frequencies in paternal lineages followed a more even distribution than in the population of
286 adults. Simulation results show that selection against homozygous males can explain these results.
287 We also found that, in situations of low levels of genetic diversity, polygyny was not related to a
288 decrease of paternally inherited genetic diversity of foetuses; rather, it was positively related to
289 higher paternally inherited genetic diversity (Shannon index) of foetuses. This effect reverted as
290 population genetic diversity increased (see Fig. 3).

291 For a polygynous mammal like the red deer, the actual level of polygyny may depend on the
292 operational sex ratio, on the degree of spatial aggregation of females and on the age structure of
293 male subpopulation that confer different mating abilities to some males relative to others (Clutton
294 Brock et al. 1982, 1988; Shuster & Wade 2003). Polygyny may have opposite consequences on the
295 genetic diversity contributed by males: on one hand (i), the decrease of the number of breeding
296 males may reduce the genetic diversity of paternal lineage (Wright 1938; Chesser 1991; Nunney
297 1991, 1993), but on the other hand (ii), an increase of male competition may prompt the
298 heterozygous advantage process (Meagher et al. 2000) and hence it may tend to increase the genetic
299 diversity of paternal lineage (e.g. Lewontin et al. 1978). Our results suggest that in situations of low
300 genetic diversity, the effect of heterozygote advantage to increase genetic diversity might outweigh
301 the effect of the lower number of breeding males to decrease it.

302 Many studies have shown a link between overall heterozygosity at molecular markers and
303 fitness (Mitton & Grant 1984; Allendorf & Leary 1986; Ledig 1986; Houle 1989; Mitton 1993;
304 Coulson et al. 1998; Hansson & Westerberg 2002). There are several hypotheses that connect hetero-
305 zygosity and fitness (Hansson & Westerberg 2002; Keller & Waller 2002). For instance, the
306 overdominance effect may confer advantages to heterozygous individuals and the dominance
307 relationship between alleles can decrease the risk of expressing recessive deleterious alleles
308 (Charlesworth & Charlesworth 1987). Heterozygote advantage can be due to an increase of

309 developmental homeostasis obtained by enzyme heterozygosity (Mitton & Grant 1984; Mitton
310 1993). Also it can be due to the advantage against infections favoured by major histocompatibility
311 complex (MHC) heterozygosity (Penn et al. 2002). However, how exactly heterozygosity acts on
312 fitness remains often unclear. For example, the correlation heterozygosity–fitness is normally
313 interpreted as the result of the connection between inbreeding and heterozygosity, but it has been
314 observed that individual heterozygosity and inbreeding coefficient can be weakly correlated
315 (Balloux et al. 2004; Slate et al. 2004).

316 In red deer, homozygous males experience disadvantages at different stages of their life
317 histories, notably as differences in mortality (Coulson et al. 1998) or breeding success (Slate et al.
318 2000). Mortality of homozygotes might have occurred for males during their lives before we took
319 our sample of adult males and may also act at the level of intrauterine mortality before we took our
320 sample of foetuses. For adult males, our results of high paternally inherited diversity are relative to
321 the sample of adult males, so they are not affected by previous mortality in the cohorts of adult
322 males. For intrauterine mortality to be relevant as an explanation for our results, we should expect
323 differences in the proportion of pregnant females among populations that relate to population
324 genetic diversity, but this was clearly not the case ($r = -0.026$, $N = 19$, $P = 0.915$). On the other
325 hand, intrauterine mortality related to population diversity could hardly explain our result of a
326 relationship between polygyny and paternally inherited genetic diversity when population genetic
327 diversity is controlled in the analysis. Therefore, the advantage of heterozygous males relevant for
328 our results should operate mainly at competition for mates, in agreement with recent results for
329 mice (Meagher et al. 2000).

330 Selection has been proposed to produce lower than expected effective population size by
331 increasing heritable based fitness-variability (Robertson 1961; Santiago & Caballero 1995). Our
332 results suggest an opposite effect of the intensity of selection to produce higher than expected

333 genetically effective population size, for which a likely mechanism is the advantage of
334 heterozygous males in the competition over mates. Some studies support the advantage of
335 heterozygous males (Keller et al. 1994; Kempenaers et al. 1996) including red deer (Slate et al.
336 2000) and that the fitness reduction experienced by homozygous males is magnified under
337 conditions of male–male competition (Meagher et al. 2000).

338 The actual effect of sexual selection to increase effective population size with respect to
339 theoretical estimations may be even higher than our data indicate. Storz et al. (2001) suggested that
340 small effective population size in one reproductive season caused by few males contributing to
341 reproduction might be compensated by higher turnover of males compared to females since they
342 have shorter reproductive lifetime, which is the case for red deer, where males have much shorter
343 reproductive lifespan than females (Clutton Brock et al. 1982; Carranza et al. 2004).

344 At the interspecific level, polygyny has been observed to relate to higher levels of genetic
345 variability in birds (Møller et al. 2008). This association might be caused by increased germline
346 mutation rate in polygynous males (Møller & Cuervo 2004; Petrie & Roberts 2007) or because male
347 breeding success may depend on genetic diversity (Mays & Hill 2004). Germline mutation rate has
348 been suggested to increase in conditions of strong sperm competition (Møller & Cuervo 2004;
349 Petrie & Roberts 2007). The occurrence of sperm competition has not been investigated in depth in
350 red deer. However, behavioural observations indicate that males strongly compete to monopolize
351 groups of females before copulation and that females normally copulate only once per ovulatory
352 cycle (Clutton-Brock et al. 1982), which suggests that the role of sperm competition may not be
353 strong in this species. But anyway, although germline mutation rate might be considered as a
354 possible cause for interspecific differences in genetic variability, it cannot explain the differences in
355 genetic variability observed here between paternal and maternal lineages, since they occur within
356 one generation. By contrast, recent studies increasingly show that the role of sexual selection

357 favouring genetic diversity rather than heritable quality may be much higher than previously
358 assumed (Mays & Hill 2004), which may contribute to explain why genetic variability is not
359 depleted under conditions of strong sexual selection (Hoffman et al. 2007; Keaeuffer et al. 2007;
360 Petrie & Roberts 2007; Kotiaho et al. 2008). Much emphasis has been put on the demographic
361 estimation of effective population size (see Engen et al. 2005 and references herein) but recent
362 works indicate that demographic estimations may not reflect actual genetic size of the breeding
363 population (Wenink et al. 1998; Hmwe et al. 2006; Keaeuffer et al. 2007), so that assumptions on
364 the relationship between polygyny, effective population size and genetic variability should be
365 revised. Our results for red deer indicate that variance in male mating success may contribute to
366 effective population size if mating success depends on genetic diversity. The generalization of these
367 results to other species deserve further research to see whether sexual selection may compensate the
368 effects of genetic drift on allele frequencies, and hence polygynous species may be less vulnerable
369 to the loss of genetic variability than previously thought (Briton et al. 1994; Frankham 2005).

370

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521 **Figure Legends**

522 **Fig. 1.** Genetic diversity in adults and parental lineages of foetuses. Figure shows the observed
523 values (mean \pm SE) for Shannon (a) and Simpson (b) diversity indices.

524 **Fig. 2.** Simulation results. Figure shows genetic diversity (mean \pm SE) of the sample of males for
525 the study populations (all males), compared with simulation results when a subsample of breeding
526 males was chosen at random from the males of every population to simulate polygyny either
527 without selection (random breeders), with low homozygous disadvantage (low selection), or with
528 high homozygous disadvantage (strong selection). See details in Methods. Mean value for all males
529 varied slightly from that shown in Fig. 1 because when computing diversity to compare it with
530 parental lineages of foetuses we avoided some markers with very small sample size (less than 5
531 genotypes, see Methods), and it was not necessary here in the simulations. Each simulation type
532 was repeated 10 times. (a) *Shannon index*: anova for differences between simulated situations: $F_{3,585}$
533 = 7.458; $P < 0.0001$. (b) *Simpson index*: anova for differences between simulated situations: $F_{3,585}$
534 = 7.579; $P < 0.0001$.

535 **Fig. 3.** Relationship between males' genetic diversity and the diversity of paternal lineage of fetuses
536 (measured by Shannon index for all estates and microsatellite markers) under two polygyny
537 conditions: high polygyny (black line) and low polygyny (grey line).

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584 **Table 1.** Comparison between adult genetic diversity and that of the parental lineage of foetuses
 585 (up, males vs. paternal lineage; down, females vs. maternal lineage). Results from repeated
 586 measures linear mixed model analyses (REML procedure) with genetic diversity as dependent
 587 variable.

Parameter	(a) Shannon index				(b) Simpson index			
	Estimate (SE)	d.f.	t	P	Estimate (SE)	d.f.	t	P
Intercept	1.307 (0.083)	15	15.700	<0.001	0.730 (0.030)	14	24.314	<0.001
Males vs. paternal lineage	0.093 (0.020)	209	4.630	<0.001	-0.017 (0.008)	207	-2.217	0.028
Intercept	1.215 (0.086)	16	14.068	<0.001	0.691 (0.032)	14	21.746	<0.001
Females vs. maternal lineage	0.192 (0.014)	219	13.195	<0.001	0.022 (0.006)	219	3.678	<0.001

588 Random factors. a) Shannon index: males vs. paternal lineage: variance \pm SE = 0.021 \pm 0.008, Wald
 589 Z = 2.517, P = 0.012 for estates; variance \pm SE = 0.067 \pm 0.029, Wald Z = 2.255, P = 0.024 for
 590 microsatellite markers; females vs. maternal lineage: variance \pm SE = 0.025 \pm 0.010, Wald Z =
 591 2.253, P = 0.012, for estates; variance \pm SE = 0.070 \pm 0.0313, Wald Z = 2.240, P = 0.025 for
 592 microsatellite markers. b) Simpson index: males vs. paternal lineage: variance \pm SE = 0.001 \pm
 593 0.001, Wald Z = 1.980, P = 0.048 for estates; variance \pm SE = 0.009 \pm 0.004, Wald Z = 2.228, P =
 594 0.026 for microsatellite markers; females vs. maternal lineage: variance \pm SE = 0.002 \pm 0.001, Wald
 595 Z = 1.927, P = 0.054 for estates; variance \pm SE = 0.010 \pm 0.004, Wald Z = 2.204, P = 0.028 for
 596 microsatellite markers.

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601 **Table 2.** Effect of parental lineage (maternal vs. paternal lineage) on offspring genetic diversity:
 602 Shannon and Simpson indices. Results from repeated measures linear mixed model analyses
 603 (REML procedure). The table shows the estimate differences in intercepts and slopes with maternal
 604 lineage as reference.

Parameter	(a) Shannon index				(b) Simpson index			
	Estimate (SE)	d.f.	t	P	Estimate (SE)	d.f.	t	P
Intercept	0.074 (0.055)	36	1.330	0.192	0.010 (0.033)	88	0.301	0.764
Paternal lineage	0.370 (0.078)	247	4.747	<0.001	0.209 (0.049)	261	4.289	<0.001
Adult diversity	0.810 (0.036)	37	22.534	<0.001	0.954 (0.044)	98	21.523	<0.001
Paternal lineage vs. adult diversity	-0.196 (0.053)	249	-3.654	<0.001	-0.239 (0.067)	262	-3.570	<0.001

605 Random factors. a) Shannon index: variance \pm SE = 0.007 \pm 0.003, Wald Z = 2.233, P = 0.026 for
 606 estates; variance \pm SE = 0.0003 \pm 0.0009, Wald Z = 0.291.043, P = 0.771 for microsatellite
 607 markers. b) Simpson index: variance \pm SE = 0.0003 \pm 0.0002, Wald Z = 1.109, P = 0.267 for
 608 estates; variance \pm SE = 0.000 \pm 0.0002, Wald Z = 0.547, P = 0.585 for microsatellite markers.

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615 **Table 3.** Effect of parental lineage (maternal vs. paternal lineage) on offspring genetic diversity
 616 after grouping those genetically connected areas. Results from repeated measures linear mixed
 617 model analyses (REML procedure). The table shows the estimate differences in intercepts and
 618 slopes with maternal lineage as reference.

Parameter	(a) Shannon index				(b) Simpson index			
	Estimate (SE)	d.f.	t	P	Estimate (SE)	d.f.	t	P
Intercept	0.099 (0.065)	41	1.505	0.140	0.009 (0.001)	59	0.032	0.975
Paternal lineage	0.347 (0.095)	139	3.643	<0.001	0.202(0.058)	142	3.507	0.001
Adult diversity	0.830 (0.040)	40	20.713	<0.001	0.976 (0.052)	64	18.885	<0.001
Paternal lineage vs. adult diversity	-0.180 (0.062)	140	-0.897	0.004	-0.229 (0.077)	142	-2.961	0.004

619 Random factors. a) Shannon index: variance \pm SE = 0.006 ± 0.003 , Wald Z = 1.733, P = 0.083 for
 620 areas; variance \pm SE = 0.0003 ± 0.001 , Wald Z = 0.319, P = 0.750 for microsatellite markers. b)
 621 Simpson index: variance \pm SE = 0.0002 ± 0.0002 , Wald Z = 0.738, P = 0.460 for areas; variance \pm
 622 SE = 0.000 ± 0.0002 , Wald Z = 0.379, P = 0.704 for microsatellite markers.

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630 **Table 4.** Effect of polygyny on paternally contributed genetic diversity. Results from a linear mixed
 631 model (REML procedure). The table shows the estimate differences in intercepts and slopes with
 632 high polygyny as reference

Parameter	(a) Shannon index				(b) Simpson index			
	Estimate (SE)	d.f.	t	P	Estimate (SE)	d.f.	t	P
Intercept	0.651 (0.095)	90	6.844	<0.001	0.271 (0.055)	119	4.891	<0.001
Low polygyny	-0.256 (0.128)	166	-2.005	0.047	-0.083 (0.078)	195	-1.072	0.285
Male diversity	0.455 (0.062)	153	7.298	<0.001	0.641 (0.076)	140	8.460	<0.001
Low polygyny vs. male diversity	0.199 (0.084)	193	2.379	0.018	0.116 (0.106)	195	1.099	0.274

633 Random factors. a) Shannon index: variance \pm SE = 0.006 \pm 0.004, Wald Z = 1.545, P = 0.122 for
 634 estates; variance \pm SE = 0.009 \pm 0.006, Wald Z = 1.559, P = 0.119 for microsatellite markers. b)
 635 Simpson index: variance \pm SE = 0.001 \pm 0.0001, Wald Z = 1.254, P = 0.210 for estates; variance \pm
 636 SE = 0.0001 \pm 0.0004, Wald Z = 0.335, P = 0.737 for microsatellite markers.

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